

Psychological Safety and Work Engagement of Senior High School Teachers in Private Schools of Davao Oriental

Miguel R. Tado

Abstract. The study unfolded the teachers' psychological safety and its influence on the work engagement of Private School Senior high School Teachers in Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data collected were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of autonomy and ownership, and team cohesion and trust were often manifested, while supportive leadership, respectful and constructive feedback, and safety to challenge the status quo are sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive, likewise, the extent of work engagement in terms of absorption and healthy work-life balance was often manifested; In contrast, vigor and a sense of meaning were sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. There was a significant correlation between teachers' psychological safety and work engagement. Domains of teachers' psychological safety in terms of respectful and constructive feedback, supportive leadership, team cohesion and trust, autonomy and ownership, and safety to challenge the status quo significantly influenced work engagement. Future research may conduct comparative studies across different school settings and demographics to understand the generalizability of findings and identify potential variations.

KEY WORDS

1. teachers' psychological safety 2. work engagement 3. work-life balance

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1. Introduction

The trends in psychological safety within private school teacher organizations across the globe have shown significant evolution in recent years. One noticeable trend is the increasing recognition of the importance of fostering psychologically safe environments in these educational institutions. Schools worldwide acknowledge that psychological safety is conducive to teacher well-being and directly impacts student success and overall school performance. The global education community is also witnessing a growing emphasis on the role of leadership in promoting psychological safety. Effective school leadership is increasingly vital for creating cultures where teachers feel comfortable expressing their ideas, concerns, and innovative

solutions. Schools focus on nurturing empathetic and supportive leadership that empowers teachers to voice their opinions without fear of retribution, enhancing psychological safety. Global events have accelerated the adoption of remote teaching and highlighted the need for flexible approaches to education. The pandemic underscored the importance of psychological safety in providing emotional support to teachers who faced unprecedented challenges while adapting to remote and hybrid teaching methods. As a result, psychological safety has become an integral part of crisis management and response strategies (Williamson et al., 2023). The digital era has brought a new dimension to psychological safety trends, as integrating technology and online teaching methods presents unique challenges. Teachers and organizations are working to ensure that online interactions and virtual classrooms remain psychologically safe for educators and students. Concerns regarding privacy, cybersecurity, and online harassment are prompting discussions on safeguarding psychological safety in the digital realm (Bordogna, 2023). Psychological safety policies must balance promoting a supportive atmosphere and allowing for the healthy exchange of ideas, even those that challenge the status quo. When psychological safety policies are too stringent or are interpreted in a way that stifles constructive debate, they can inadvertently undermine work engagement. The key is to foster an environment where teachers feel safe and encouraged to share their thoughts, explore innovative teaching methods, and engage in professional development, ultimately enhancing their work engagement while ensuring the well-being of the educational community as a whole (Windlinger et al., 2021). In the Philippines, strict psychological safety policies inadvertently promote a culture of conformity, where teachers are discouraged from taking calculated risks or pushing boundaries in their teaching approaches. Teachers who feel they must always adhere to a partic-

ular set of norms and practices may become less engaged, as they need more room for creativity and experimentation in their classrooms. Additionally, providing teachers with psychological support and resources for managing stress, such as counseling services or well-being programs, can help improve their overall mental and emotional well-being, subsequently increasing their work engagement. Professional development, financial support, recognition, and well-being initiatives can ultimately contribute to more engaged and motivated senior high school teachers in Davao Oriental, fostering a conducive environment for quality education (Pan et al., 2023). Bas and Tabancali (2020) determine the level of the teacher's voice and examine the relationships between voice, five-factor personality traits, and psychological safety. Results showed that the level of the teacher's voice was at level "Often," and there were significant and positive correlations between agreeableness, extraversion, emotional stability and openness to experience, and teacher's voice; and also between psychological safety and teacher's voice; and lastly, between psychological safety and agreeableness and emotional stability. Significant and positive relationships were found between teacher voice, psychological safety, and personality, while the strength of the relationships was low. Therefore, future studies might focus on other individual and organizational factors related to the teacher's voice. Private school senior high school teachers in Davao Oriental, located in the Davao Region, encounter various challenges that impact their work engagement. One significant challenge is the need to adapt to changing educational paradigms and meet the demands of a diverse student population. The shift to online or hybrid learning, intensified by the COVID-19 pandemic, has required teachers to quickly acquire digital skills and adapt to new teaching methods, which can be mentally and emotionally taxing. Another challenge lies in the relatively lower compensation and job secu-

rity in private schools, which can lead to financial concerns and lower job satisfaction among teachers. This economic strain may contribute to stress and reduced work engagement. Innovative strategies can be employed to address these challenges and boost work engagement among private school senior high school teachers in Davao Oriental. Schools can invest in professional development programs focusing on technology integration and remote teaching, providing teachers with the skills and confidence to navigate digital learning environments effectively.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Psychological Safety*—Psychological safety, a critical workplace and educational concept, allows individuals to express thoughts and feedback without fearing negative repercussions. It's tied to trust and respect within a group, fostering problem-solving and innovation. Dramanu et al. (2020) found psychological safety and flexibility significantly predict work engagement in teachers, recommending interventions to enhance these aspects. Shahid and Din (2021) highlight the role of leadership in fostering psychological safety, suggesting a collaborative school culture enhances this safety, which is crucial for team learning and organizational outcomes. Psychological safety encourages collaboration, creativity, and well-being, enhancing productivity.

1.1.2. *Respectful and Constructive Feedback*—Respectful and constructive feedback, integral to psychological safety, involves open communication and mutual respect, fostering growth and improvement. Adams (2023) linked principal support to a climate of teacher psychological safety, enhancing student support. Kulikova and Maliy (2017) emphasized teachers' emotional stability and creative thinking in designing a safe educational environment. Itzchakov et al. (2023) found listening training improves relational climate and psychological safety among teachers. Zhu et al. (2019)

showed empowering leadership boosts teachers' innovative behavior through psychological empowerment, moderated by team psychological safety. Feedback characterized by empathy and active listening nurtures trust and collaboration, essential for continuous improvement.

1.1.3. *Supportive Leadership*—Supportive leadership promotes a secure, valued, and communicative environment. Liu et al. (2023) identified job resources, demands, and self-efficacy as significant to STEM teachers' job satisfaction. Windlinger and Zuger (2021) linked job demands and resources to well-being in extended education services. Khandakar et al. (2019) found HRM practices positively impact informal workplace learning. Wang and Peng (2022) demonstrated shared leadership enhances creativity through psychological safety but may increase role stress. Supportive leadership fosters an atmosphere of trust, enhancing teamwork, innovation, and well-being.

1.1.4. *Team Cohesion and Trust*—Team cohesion and trust are vital for psychological safety, allowing open sharing of thoughts without fear. Hamm et al. (2021) showed strong ties and relational trust among teachers enhance efficacy beliefs. Waber et al. (2022) identified open communication as core to trust in teacher education. Pinheiro et al. (2023) found transformational leadership and team cohesion crucial for team learning. Kolleck et al. (2021) linked teacher collaboration networks to trust relationships. Wang et al. (2022) emphasized social presence in classroom community cohesion. Cohesion and trust foster a psychologically safe environment, enhancing collaboration and innovation.

1.1.5. *Autonomy and Ownership*—Autonomy and ownership empower individuals, fostering a sense of control and responsibility. Ertürk (2023) found teacher autonomy predicts commitment to the profession. Valdmann et al. (2020) defined teacher ownership through internalization of motivational contexts. Gülsen

and Atay (2022) showed dialogic reflections enhance EFL teachers' autonomy. Chung (2023) highlighted Finnish teachers' autonomy due to research-based education. DiLucchio and Leaman (2022) found teacher research projects boost instructional confidence and autonomy. Autonomy and ownership encourage open dialogue, risk-taking, and strong commitment, enhancing productivity and well-being.

1.2. Theoretical Framework—Given the variables presented in the study, this study is anchored on the following theories. These theoretical frameworks offer valuable lenses to understand and analyze various aspects of work engagement, employee well-being, and the factors influencing them in organizational and workplace contexts. Researchers and practitioners can apply these theories to design interventions and strategies that enhance work engagement and the overall quality of work life. The Job-demands Resources or JD-R Model created by Bakker and Demerouti (2006) is a comprehensive framework that examines the interplay between job demands and job resources and their impact on employees' well-being and performance. According to this model, job demands are aspects of work that require sustained effort and can lead to burnout if excessive, while job resources are factors that support employees and enhance their engagement. The model posits that balancing these demands and resources influences work-related outcomes. It helps us understand how work-related factors like workload and social support can affect employees' engagement and overall well-being (Windlinger, 2021). Self-determination theory by Ryan and Deci (1985) is a psychological theory that explores the role of intrinsic motivation, autonomy, and relatedness in driving human behavior and well-being. It suggests that individuals are more engaged and satisfied when they feel a sense of independence, competence, and relatedness in their activities. In the context of work, SDT emphasizes that employees who are

intrinsically motivated, have a sense of choice and control over their tasks, and feel connected to others at work are more likely to experience high levels of work engagement (Williams et al., 2023). Social Exchange Theory. This theory by George Homans (1958) centers on the idea that individuals engage in social relationships and exchanges that involve reciprocal actions. In the workplace, employees exchange efforts, loyalty, and commitment for rewards, recognition, and support from their organizations. The quality of these social exchanges can impact employees' attitudes and behaviors. When applied to work engagement, a positive social exchange, where employees perceive support and fairness, can enhance their engagement and commitment to their organizations (Bordogna, 2023). Organizational Support Theory, authored by (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Eisenberger Stinglhamber, 2011 Shore Shore, 1995), focuses on employees' perceptions of the support they receive from their organizations. It posits that employees who feel supported by their organizations are more likely to reciprocate with positive attitudes and behaviors. This theory underscores the significance of organizational support in shaping employees' well-being, job satisfaction, and engagement. In the context of work engagement, when employees perceive that their organization values and supports their well-being, they are more likely to be engaged in their work (Khandakar et al., 2019). Conservation of Resources Theory by Stevan Hobfoll (1980) suggests that individuals strive to acquire, protect, and build resources (e.g., social, psychological, or material resources) to prevent stress and promote well-being. In the workplace, this theory implies that employees with access to resources are better equipped to handle the demands of their jobs. For work engagement, it implies that psychological safety, as a resource, can be pivotal in maintaining or enhancing employees' well-being and engagement, as it provides a sense of security and support, which helps

protect their existing resources (Wang Peng, 2022). Figure 1 below shows the variables in the study. In this study, applying various psychological theories to the context of psychological safety and work engagement among private school teachers was instrumental in understanding the dynamics at play in this specific educational setting. The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model was highly relevant as it allows us to dissect the delicate balance between the demands placed on private school teachers, such as high academic standards and workload, and the resources available, including psychological safety. The model helps us recognize that psychological safety, as a resource, can mitigate the potential detrimental effects of excessive job demands and promote work engagement among teachers. Self-determination theory (SDT) provides insights into teachers' intrinsic motivation and autonomy. In private schools, where academic excellence is often emphasized, SDT can explain how psychological safety, by fostering a sense of autonomy in expressing opinions and concerns, can positively influence teachers' intrinsic motivation and, consequently, their work engagement. Social Exchange Theory was particularly pertinent when considering the reciprocity and mutual expectations between private school teachers and their institutions. When teachers perceive that their contributions are met with psychological safety, support, and recognition, it encourages a positive social exchange that enhances their work engagement. Organizational Support Theory aligns with the notion that psychological safety can be a form of support the organization

provides. When private school teachers perceive this support, it positively influences their work engagement, as they feel valued, secure, and encouraged to contribute to their fullest potential. The Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory underscores the significance of preserving resources to maintain well-being. In this context, psychological safety can be viewed as a resource private school teachers seek to protect. When they perceive psychological safety in their work environment, it maintains their existing resources, enhances well-being, and promotes work engagement. The dependent variable of this study was psychological safety, based on the following indicators: respectful and constructive feedback, supportive leadership, team cohesion and trust, autonomy and ownership, and safety to challenge the status. The dependent variable is work engagement in terms of the following indicators: vigor, absorption, sense of meaning and purpose, and healthy work-life balance. A psychologically safe environment fosters a space where students feel comfortable seeking answers and clarification, which helps to improve their understanding and overall performance. Students are more likely to thrive when they feel safe asking questions, seeking clarification, and expressing their thoughts. These theories provide valuable frameworks for comprehending the relationships between psychological safety and work engagement among private school teachers. They enable researchers and educators to assess, analyze, and improve the work environment, ultimately fostering a more engaged and satisfied private school teaching workforce.

1.3. Statement of the Problem—The study was purposely conducted to determine the extent of teachers' teaching psychological safety and its influence on work engagement of Private

School Senior high School Teachers in Davao Oriental Schools Division. This specifically sought to answer the following statement of the problem:

- (1) What is the extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of;
 - (1) respectful and constructive feedback;

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

- (2) supportive leadership;
 - (3) team cohesion and trust;
 - (4) autonomy and ownership, and
 - (5) safety to challenge the status quo?
- (2) What is the extent of work engagement in terms of;
 - (1) vigor;
 - (2) absorption;
 - (3) sense of meaning; and
 - (4) healthy work-life balance?
 - (3) Is there a significant relationship between teachers’ psychological safety and work engagement?
 - (4) Which among the domains of teachers’ psychological safety significantly influences work engagement?

1.4. *Hypotheses*—To provide empirical evidence given the posed theoretical and conceptual frameworks as claimed by the study, null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance, stating: Ho 1: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ psychological safety and work engagement; and, Ho 2: None of the domains of teachers’ psychological safety significantly influence work engagement. The study’s quantitative analysis on the extent of psychological safety and its influence on work engagement among Private School Senior high School Teachers in Davao Oriental Schools Division holds significance for various stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers,

parents, and future researchers. Results were of importance to the following: School Principals and Administrators. The findings were invaluable for school administrators as they can help shape policies and practices that promote a psychologically safe and engaging environment for teachers. Understanding the dynamics of psychological safety and work engagement could enable administrators to foster supportive leadership, recognize and address teacher concerns, and institute initiatives that enhance their teaching staff’s overall well-being and performance. Teachers. For teachers, the study offers insights into the factors influencing their work engagement and highlights the importance of

psychological safety in their professional lives. With this knowledge, teachers can advocate for conducive work environments, which ultimately contribute to their job satisfaction and overall effectiveness in the classroom. Private school stakeholders, including parents, students, and school boards, benefit from this research by understanding how psychological safety and work engagement impact the quality of education. They can appreciate teachers' critical role in student development and academic success. Informed stakeholders can support measures that promote a positive and empowering work environment for teachers, leading to better educational outcomes. Future Researchers. Future researchers can build on this study by exploring additional dimensions of psychological safety and work engagement or by investigating the impact of interventions designed to enhance these factors. This study provides a foundation for a continued examination of teacher well-being and effectiveness within the private school context, ultimately contributing to the ongoing improvement of the education system. In conclusion, this study's significance extends to a broad spectrum of stakeholders by offering practical insights, recommendations, and a research framework that can inform decision-making, teaching practices, and future scholarly investigations related to student governance and learner safety in educational institutions.

2. Methodology

Research method refers to the systematic approach or strategy researchers use to conduct their investigations. It outlines how data is gathered, analyzed, and interpreted in a structured way to answer research questions and achieve research objectives. Essentially, it was the plan or roadmap for a research study. In this context, understanding the research method was essential for both researchers and readers as it determines the validity and reliability of the study's findings and contributes to the broader body of knowledge in the field of inquiry. This aims to elucidate the key components and considerations associated with the chosen research method, setting the stage for a comprehensive exploration of the research methodology employed in the study. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design was a comprehensive research approach that combined several key elements. It was non-experimental, for it does not involve the manipulation of variables or establishing a cause-and-effect relationship. Instead, it focuses on observing and measuring existing phenomena as they naturally occur. Second, it was descriptive, aiming to provide a detailed and systematic account of a particular subject or topic. This involves collecting data through surveys, observations, or existing records to describe and summarize the characteristics, behaviors, or conditions under investigation. Third, it was correlational, which means it sought to identify relationships or associations between variables. This involves analyzing data to determine whether changes in one variable are related to changes in another without imply-

ing causation. The researcher used the quantitative descriptive-correlational technique to achieve the study's objectives and gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) defined quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It was formed from a deductive approach where the emphasis is placed on testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacked the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Lastly, it was predictive, often aiming to make informed predictions or forecasts based on the identified correlations. By understanding the relationships between variables, researchers can use this knowledge to make reasonable predictions about future outcomes or trends (Creswel, 2014). In the study titled "Psychological Safety and Work Engagement of Senior High School Teachers in Private Schools of Davao Oriental," a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design is employed to explore and understand the complex relationships between psychological safety and work engagement among senior high school teachers in private schools within the Davao Oriental region. This research design facilitates the collection and analysis of data to describe the current state of psychological safety and work engagement in the selected schools without manipulating any variables, making it ideal for observing naturally occurring phenomena in their real-world context. By examining these variables descriptively and establishing correlations, the study aims to understand the existing dynamics comprehensively. Furthermore, this design's predictive aspect helps identify potential factors that can forecast or influence psychological safety and work engagement. Through this approach,

the research offers valuable insights for educational institutions, policymakers, and school administrators to enhance the well-being and performance of senior high school teachers in private schools in Davao Oriental.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Senior High School Teachers in the Private Schools in the Davao Oriental area. He used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 80 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from each Private Secondary School surrounding the area. After being selected through randomization, respondents were notified both through online platforms and in-person, taking into account the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they received an orientation regarding the study's objectives and its significance to their professional development. The selection of teacher-respondents was based on the assumption that they are actively involved and presently employed in private schools. They were expected to strongly engage with the policies and regulations governing private school systems and the day-to-day management and execution of various school-based learning programs, projects, and activities designed to enhance students' development within the framework of school-based management within private school settings. The qualifications for participation in this study were rooted in the expectation that they had made significant contributions, extending beyond their primary roles in curriculum delivery, implementation, and governance, by actively participating in various educational activities. These contributions were typically discussed during school faculty meetings, group sessions, and committee meetings, all to improve the school environment and students' educational experiences during the new regular learning system in the academic year 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school manage-

ment and curriculum development delivery system.

2.3. Research Instrument—The instrument employed in this research study was meticulously crafted through a comprehensive review of existing literature and related studies. The researcher dedicated substantial effort to gathering and analyzing relevant literature, extracting key concepts that guided the instrument’s development and fortified its alignment with the designated strands. This thorough procedure contributed to creating a well-structured set of questionnaire items, thereby bolstering the overall validity of the instrument and mitigating potential challenges to its reliability. The authors argued that items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts, each consisting of indicators of psycho-

logical safety in terms of respectful and constructive feedback, supportive leadership, team cohesion and trust, autonomy and ownership, and safety to challenge the status quo. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured work engagement in terms of vigor, absorption, sense of meaning and purpose, and healthy work-life balance. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.899, which means an 89.9 percent confidence level in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of psychological safety. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The psychological safety is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The psychological safety is often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The psychological safety is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The psychological safety is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The psychological safety is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of work engagement, a 5-point Likert scale was used in

this study, as presented below;

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The statements provide a clear overview of the sequential steps that define the data collection process. This approach was vital to ensure safety and mitigate any potential risks associated with gathering relevant data, especially given the current context of ongoing in-person interactions. Permission to conduct the study. In the second

week of December 2023, the researcher initiated the process of conceptualizing the content and objectives of the thesis proposal. Subsequently, she prepared various documents, including request letters, for the study. The research study strictly adhered to established ethical data collection procedures, as Creswell (2004) outlined, and followed the health protocols mandated by the IATF’s policy. As the research proposal was

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1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The work engagement is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The work engagement is not manifested

approved by the panel of members and the college dean in the last week of February to the first week of March 2024, the researcher composed and submitted a formal letter seeking permission to collect data and conduct the study within the Private Secondary Schools to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, following the proper channels. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the first week of April 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime during the first week of May 2024 and further deepen the analysis to make more meaning with

the interpretations of results during the second week of May 2024.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are a cornerstone in upholding the integrity and safeguarding the rights of individuals within research and educational pursuits. In voluntary participation, ethics reinforce the principle that individuals should make a deliberate, uncoerced choice to engage in any activity or study. Central to this ethical framework is informed consent, which entails furnishing participants with thorough details regarding the nature, objectives, potential risks, and benefits of the activity or research. Voluntary Participation. The researcher’s duty in conveying information about voluntary participation involves providing clear and comprehensive insights into the study and the respondent’s role within it. Researchers must guarantee that participants fully grasp the research’s purpose, goals, procedures, and any potential risks or benefits associated with their involvement. It was crucial to emphasize that participation was entirely optional, and respondents retained the freedom to decline or withdraw from the study at any stage without facing the consequences. Privacy and Confidentiality. The researcher’s task in informing the respondent about privacy and confidentiality involves communicating how the respondent’s personal information and data were handled throughout the research process. Privacy measures, such as using identification numbers in-

stead of names, were often implemented. Additionally, researchers explained any data storage and security protocols in place to protect the confidentiality of information. This communication ensures that participants feel secure in sharing their thoughts and experiences, fostering trust and ethical research practices.

Informed Consent Process. The researcher conveyed the study's purpose, objectives, procedures, and potential risks and benefits in simple and understandable language. Participants should also be informed of their right to ask questions and seek clarification. Researchers must underscore that participation was entirely voluntary, and participants can decline or withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences. Obtaining informed consent typically involves securing written consent from participants, signifying their willingness to participate while fully comprehending the research's nature and implications. This procedure was indispensable to ensure that participants make an informed and voluntary choice to engage in the study, upholding ethical standards and respecting their autonomy and rights throughout the research process.

Risks. The researcher identifies and describes these risks clearly and understandably, ensuring that participants are fully aware of what they might encounter during the research process. This includes physical, psychological, emotional, or social risks that could arise from their involvement. Importantly, researchers must also explain the steps taken to minimize or mitigate these risks and the available support systems to address any issues that may arise.

Benefits. The researcher describes how the research could contribute to knowledge, address important issues, or potentially benefit society or a specific group. Additionally, she highlighted any personal benefits that participants might gain, such as increased self-awareness, improved skills, or access to valuable resources. This transparency and clarity in communicating benefits are es-

sential to engaging and motivating individuals to participate in the study willingly and ethically.

Plagiarism. In addressing plagiarism, the researcher's role encompasses elucidating the significance of academic integrity and the ethical principles governing the utilization of others' work and ideas. Researchers should clarify that plagiarism involves presenting someone else's words, thoughts, or creations as one's own without due attribution. Additionally, the researcher offered guidance on the correct methods of citing and referencing sources, illustrating how to prevent plagiarism and uphold ethical research standards. This information ensured that respondents grasped the value of originality and proper source attribution in research, highlighting the imperative of honesty and integrity in academic and professional pursuits.

Fabrication. The researcher made it clear that fabrication undermines the integrity of the research process and can lead to severe academic and professional repercussions. He stressed the importance of reporting accurate and truthful results, even if they do not align with the desired or expected outcomes. Providing this information ensures that respondents understand the ethical imperative of maintaining the highest standards of honesty and integrity in research that was essential for the credibility and reliability of scientific and scholarly work.

Falsification. The researcher informed the respondent that falsification involves conveying the ethical principles and consequences associated with altering, manipulating, or misrepresenting research data or findings. Researchers explained that falsification undermines the credibility and trustworthiness of research and can have serious academic and professional repercussions. It is essential to emphasize the importance of accurately reporting data and findings, even if they do not align with expectations or hypotheses.

Conflict of Interest. The researcher's obligation in communicating with the respondent about a conflict of interest involves disclosing any situations in which

the researcher or any involved party may have conflicting interests that could potentially influence the research findings or compromise the study's impartiality. The researcher engaged in a transparent conversation, explicitly stating any financial, personal, or professional connections or affiliations that could impact the research process or results. It is essential to emphasize that disclosing conflicts of interest is a fundamental ethical responsibility to uphold the research's credibility and integrity. This transparency empowers respondents to evaluate the potential influence of such disputes on the study's fairness, enabling them to make well-informed assessments regarding the research's reliability and trustworthiness. Deceit. The researcher's task in informing the respondent about deceit involves being honest and transparent about the research objectives, procedures, and any information that might intentionally mislead or deceive participants. Researchers must clearly and accurately explain the study's purpose and any deception involved in the research process. In cases where deception is necessary for the study's goals, researchers should debrief participants after their involvement, revealing the true nature and purpose of the study and addressing any concerns or misconceptions. Ethical research demands that respondents are not manipulated or misled in any way that could harm their well-being or autonomy, and maintaining trust between researchers and participants is of utmost importance to ensure the ethical conduct of the study. Permission from the Organization/Location. The researcher's role in informing the respondent about acquiring permission from the organization or location involves elucidating the essential steps and protocols for securing authorization to conduct research within a specific organizational or site setting. Researchers should emphasize the significance of obtaining official permission, underscoring its vital role as an ethical and procedural requirement. This entails explaining the potential implications of the

research on the organization, assuring the confidential handling of data, and providing a comprehensive account of any specific guidelines or procedures that must be adhered to during the research process. By furnishing this information, researchers ensure that respondents understand the ethical and logistical considerations of obtaining the necessary permissions. This also lets participants know their rights and responsibilities when conducting research within a particular organizational or location context. Authorship. The researcher's responsibility in enlightening respondents about authorship involves clarifying the criteria and principles governing authorship within scholarly publications. The researcher explained the requirements for being recognized as an author, which typically include substantial contributions to various aspects of the research, such as design, data collection, analysis, and manuscript preparation. It was crucial to convey that authorship was based on genuine intellectual contributions and merit rather than mere affiliations or roles within the research team.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1) regarding the extent of psychological safety and statement problem number two (2) regarding the extent of work engagement. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between psychological safety and work engagement. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the indicators of psychological safety that significantly influence work engagement (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results were yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the researcher addresses the collection of data and its subsequent presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Tabular and textual formats are employed to enhance the depth of analysis and facilitate the extraction of meaningful implications. Further, these presentations serve as supporting evidence for the hypothesis put forth.

3.1. Psychological Safety—Psychological safety is a critical concept in the workplace and educational environments. It refers to the extent to which individuals feel comfortable, secure, and confident in expressing their thoughts, ideas, concerns, and feedback without fearing negative consequences. In psychologically safe settings, individuals can voice their opinions, engage in open and honest discussions, take risks, and contribute to problem-solving and innovation. This concept is closely tied to trust and respect within a group or organization, where individuals believe their contributions are valued and won't face ridicule, humiliation, or retribution for speaking up. Dramanu et al. (2020) investigated how senior high school teachers' perception of their psychological safety in their schools predicted their work engagement and the moderating role of psychological flexibility. Both psychological flexibility and perception of psychological safety were significant positive predictors of senior high school teachers' work engagement. Also, psychological flexibility significantly moderated the effect of psychological safety on work engagement. The study concluded that psychological safety is an essential determinant of the perception of psychological safety and work engagement.

3.2. Respectful and Constructive Feedback—Table 1 presents the extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of respectful and constructive feedback. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean

ratings of indicators which are as follows: provides guidance on how to enhance performance or address areas of concern (4.10) is always manifested; it is given promptly and in the right setting, ensuring that individuals can apply the feedback effectively and understand its relevance (3.20), feedback is directed at observable behaviors or results, making it more objective and actionable, rather than making personal judgments (3.15), feedback is delivered with consideration for the individual's feelings, opinions, and efforts, fostering a sense of respect and dignity (3.00) and feedback is seen as an opportunity for discussion and learning, encouraging open communication and active listening between the giver and receiver (3.00) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes that the extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of respectful and constructive feedback is sometimes manifested; thus, it is moderately extensive. Respectful and constructive feedback, as a component of psychological safety, embodies the principles of open communication and mutual respect within a group or organization. This concept revolves around the idea that individuals are free to express their thoughts and ideas in psychologically safe environments and are encouraged to do so respectfully and constructively. It involves providing positive or critical feedback to foster growth, learning, and improvement rather than demeaning or demoralizing the recipient.

Training teachers to listen may enable them to experience increasingly attentive and open peer relationships at work. In the present re-

search, we examined the outcomes of a year-long listening training on school teachers' listening abilities and its downstream consequences

Table 1. The Extent of Senior High School Teachers' Psychological Safety in terms of Respectful and Constructive Feedback

No	Respectful and Constructive Feedback	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	feedback is delivered with consideration for the individual's feelings, opinions, and efforts, fostering a sense of respect and dignity.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	feedback is directed at observable behaviors or results, making it more objective and actionable rather than making personal judgments.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	provides guidance on how to enhance performance or address areas of concern.	4.10	Extensive
4	it is given promptly and in the right setting, ensuring that individuals can apply the feedback effectively and understand its relevance.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
5	feedback is seen as an opportunity for discussion and learning, encouraging open communication and active listening between the giver and receiver.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.29	Moderately Extensive

on their relational climate, autonomy, and psychological safety. The measures included indicators of a supportive relational environment essential to teacher well-being: autonomy, psychological safety, and relational energy. Results of growth curve modeling showed linear increases in all three outcomes, such that more listening training corresponded to a more positive relational climate. Specifically, the teachers reported increasingly higher quality listening from their group-member teachers and felt more autonomy-satisfied, psychologically safe, and relationally energetic. Furthermore, latent growth curve modeling indicated that the teachers' listening perception was positively and significantly associated with all three outcomes. We concluded that listening training is associated with teachers perceiving higher

quality listening from their peers and, therefore, feeling more autonomy-satisfied, psychologically safe, and relationally energetic and discussing theoretical and practical implications (Itzchakov et al., 2023). The study of Adams (2023) tested the relationship between Principal Support of Teacher Psychological Needs (PSTPN) and a need-supportive instructional climate. "PSTP is associated with school differences in student reported autonomy-support, competence-support, and relational-support; A climate of teacher psychological safety mediates the relationship between PSTPN and student reported autonomy-support, competence-support, and relational-support; A climate of organizational commitment mediates the relationship between PSTPN and student reported autonomy-support, competence-support, and

relational-support.” Zhu et al. (2019) investigate the mediating role of teachers’ psychological empowerment and the moderating role of team psychological safety in the relationship between empowering leadership and teachers’ innovative behavior in teaching and research groups (TR groups) as professional learning communities. The multilevel model results show that empowering leadership improves teachers’ innovative behavior by increasing teachers’ psychological empowerment, which is not influenced by team psychological safety. A supplementary analysis shows that the relationship between team psychological safety and teachers’ innovative behavior is also mediated by psychological empowerment.

3.3. Supportive Leadership—Supportive leadership, as a component of psychological safety, is characterized by a solid commitment to creating a work or educational environment where individuals feel secure, valued, and encouraged to voice their opinions, concerns, and ideas without fear of reprisals. Supportive leaders exhibit qualities such as empathy, approachability, active listening, and a genuine interest in the well-being and growth of their team members. They offer guidance and resources to help individuals succeed, fostering a culture of trust and respect. This leadership style pro-

Extended education services are expanding in Switzerland. Their quality depends on the working conditions and well-being of staff. Windlinger and Zuger (2021) examined the relationships between job demands, job resources, and well-being using the job demands-resources (JD-R) model. Results supported the motivational and health impairment processes proposed by the JD-R model, although not consistently for both measurement intervals. The findings highlight the importance of significantly focusing on working conditions when extended education services expand. Supportive lead-

ership is a Psychological safety, which is the shared belief that the team is safe for interpersonal risk-taking. Critical team events such as conflict and faultlines (hypothetical lines that split a team into subgroups) should impact psychological safety. Previous research has shown the benefits of task conflict on team outcomes under certain conditions and the consistently negative effects of demographic faultline strength on team outcomes. Results of multilevel model tests showed that relationship conflict (but not task conflict) and faultlines decreased psychological safety. However, when

motes open communication, collaboration, and a sense of belonging, motivating individuals to contribute their best (Windlinger, 2021). Table 2 presents the extent of senior high school teachers’ psychological safety regarding supportive leadership. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: leaders offer feedback and guidance to help individuals grow and develop, and they do so respectfully and helpfully (4.10) and supportive leaders actively listen to their team members and demonstrate empathy toward their feelings, experiences, and challenges (3.45) are oftentimes manifested; while, a supportive leader creates a climate where individuals feel safe to express their thoughts, concerns, and ideas without fear of negative consequences (3.20), supportive leaders empower team members by delegating tasks and responsibilities, allowing them to take ownership of their work and decisions (3.20) and leaders who foster psychological safety encourage continuous learning, innovation, and a shared commitment to personal and collective development (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes that the extent of senior high school teachers’ psychological safety in terms of supportive leadership is sometimes manifested; thus, it is moderately extensive.

ership is a Psychological safety, which is the shared belief that the team is safe for interpersonal risk-taking. Critical team events such as conflict and faultlines (hypothetical lines that split a team into subgroups) should impact psychological safety. Previous research has shown the benefits of task conflict on team outcomes under certain conditions and the consistently negative effects of demographic faultline strength on team outcomes. Results of multilevel model tests showed that relationship conflict (but not task conflict) and faultlines decreased psychological safety. However, when

Table 2. The Extent of Senior High School Teachers’ Psychological Safety in terms of Supportive Leadership

No	Supportive Leadership	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	a supportive leader creates a climate where individuals feel safe to express their thoughts, concerns, and ideas without fear of negative consequences.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
2	supportive leaders actively listen to their team members and demonstrate empathy toward their feelings, experiences, and challenges.	3.45	Extensive
3	leaders offer feedback and guidance to help individuals grow and develop, and they do so respectfully and helpfully.	4.10	Extensive
4	supportive leaders empower team members by delegating tasks and responsibilities, allowing them to take ownership of their work and decisions.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
5	leaders who foster psychological safety encourage continuous learning, innovation, and a shared commitment to personal and collective development.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.39	Moderately Extensive

teachers belonged to the principal’s in-group as compared to an out-group, task conflict had no negative effect on psychological safety (Gerlach and Gockel, 2018). When leaders provide support and encouragement, they enable psychological safety, as team members are more likely to express themselves and engage in constructive dialogue. Supportive leadership plays a pivotal role in fostering an atmosphere where everyone feels valued, their voices heard, and their contributions appreciated, ultimately enhancing teamwork, innovation, and overall well-being.

3.4. *Team Cohesion and Trust*—Team cohesion and trust, as components of psychological safety, are crucial for fostering a supportive

and inclusive environment in a group or organization. Team cohesion refers to the extent to which members of a team feel connected, committed to a shared goal, and work together seamlessly. Trust, on the other hand, represents the belief that team members can rely on each other, be vulnerable, and expect mutual support and respect. These components are foundational to psychological safety because when team members are cohesive and trust one another, they feel more secure in sharing their thoughts, ideas, and concerns without the fear of judgment or negative consequences. Table 3 presents the extent of senior high school teachers’ psychological safety in terms of team co-

hesion and trust. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: team members work together towards shared objectives, which helps align their efforts and promote mutual trust in achieving those goals (4.10), trust in colleagues and leaders allows team members to be more open, take risks, and express their ideas and concerns without fear of judgment or betrayal (3.45) and team members feel a strong sense of connection and unity, enhancing their ability to collaborate and support one another (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, in an environment built on trust, team members can engage in open and candid discussions, address conflicts constructively, and provide honest feedback (3.10) and when team members trust one another and work cohesively, they are more engaged in their work and demonstrate higher levels of perfor-

Team teaching as a form of collaborative teaching practice is increasingly employed in teacher education. Positive and trusting relationships with the team partner and the mentor teacher are at the core of such internships and form the basis for optimal learning experiences and successful cooperation in the practicum. However, trust has been little explored in pre-service teacher education. Waber et al.(2022) addressed students' perceptions of trust in their team partner and their mentor teacher. The results reveal that many different facets contributed to student teachers' perceptions of trust. These could be divided into the two main dimensions: interpersonal and professional trust. Open communication based on mutual appreciation and respect was the core element of a 'trusting' relationship from the students' perspective. In recent years, teachers around the world have been increasingly confronted with various expectations concerning the improvement of their classroom practices and school activities. One factor widely acknowledged to facilitate school

mance and productivity (3.00) are sometimes manifested, The overall mean rating of 3.41 denotes that the extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of team cohesion and trust is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Hamm et al., (2021) examines the ties of sixth-grade teachers to their interdisciplinary team colleagues and explores the dimensions of their efficacy beliefs for their own and their colleagues' teaching. Greater tie strength in fall predicted greater relational trust at winter and spring. Tie strength to teammates in fall predicted greater efficacy beliefs for classroom management and collective efficacy across the year, through greater relational trust midway through the year. The findings expand theorizing and reveal organizational processes that may be used to leverage teacher efficacy beliefs.

and classroom improvement is a strong collaborative culture among teachers. As such, teachers are expected to work in teacher teams, collaborate closely with colleagues, co-construct classroom practices, and thus strengthen trust relationships within the team. A growing number of researchers have analyzed how teachers address these expectations. They suggest that there is a link between teachers' embeddedness in collaboration networks and teachers' trust relationships. Kolleck et al. (2021) seeks to contribute to the research literature by presenting the results of Social Network Analyses (SNA) and exponential random graph models (ERGMs) on teacher collaboration in nine secondary schools in Germany. Results of our analyses suggest that a high amount of TT is not necessarily related to a higher degree of trust among teachers at the school level. However, a high involvement of teachers in TT is related positively to their being perceived as trustworthy. Furthermore, the emergence of trust relations in teacher networks depends on general network charac-

Table 3. Extent of Senior High School Teachers’ Psychological Safety in terms of Supportive Leadership

No	Supportive Leadership	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	team members feel a strong sense of connection and unity, enhancing their ability to collaborate and support one another.	3.40	Extensive
2	trust in colleagues and leaders allows team members to be more open, take risks, and express their ideas and concerns without fear of judgment or betrayal.	3.45	Extensive
3	team members work together towards shared objectives, which helps align their efforts and promote mutual trust in achieving those goals.	4.10	Extensive
4	in an environment built on trust, team members can engage in open and candid discussions, address conflicts constructively, and provide honest feedback.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
5	when team members trust one another and work cohesively, they are more engaged in their work and demonstrate higher levels of performance and productivity.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.41	Extensive

teristics, such as homophily, reciprocity, and transitivity.

3.5. *Autonomy and Ownership*—Autonomy and ownership, as components of psychological safety, represent the degree to which individuals within a group or organization feel empowered, accountable, and responsible for their actions and decisions. Autonomy involves having the freedom and independence to make choices, express creativity, and take ownership of one’s work or contributions. Table 4 presents the extent of senior high school teachers’ psychological safety in terms of autonomy and ownership. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: a psychologically safe environment promotes self-direction, where individuals are trusted to manage their tasks and work independently (4.10), in a psychologically safe

environment, individuals have the freedom to make choices and take ownership of their tasks and responsibilities (3.40) and taking ownership of tasks and projects can lead to a greater sense of pride and fulfillment when they are successfully completed (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, empowering individuals with autonomy and allowing them to take ownership of their work is often linked to increased job satisfaction and a more positive work experience (3.30) and when individuals take ownership of their work, they feel a greater sense of responsibility for their outcomes and are held accountable for their performance (3.15) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.47 denotes that the extent of senior high school teachers’ psychological safety in terms of autonomy and ownership is oftentimes manifested and, thus, extensive.

Table 4. Extent of Senior High School Teachers' Psychological Safety in terms of Autonomy and Ownership

No	Autonomy and Ownership	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	in a psychologically safe environment, individuals have the freedom to make choices and take ownership of their tasks and responsibilities.	3.40	Extensive
2	when individuals take ownership of their work, they feel a greater sense of responsibility for their outcomes and are held accountable for their performance.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
3	a psychologically safe environment promotes self-direction, where individuals are trusted to manage their tasks and work independently.	4.10	Extensive
4	taking ownership of tasks and projects can lead to a greater sense of pride and fulfillment when they are successfully completed.	3.40	Extensive
5	empowering individuals with autonomy and allowing them to take ownership of their work is often linked to increased job satisfaction and a more positive work experience.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.47	Extensive

Ownership refers to individuals' sense of responsibility and pride in their roles, tasks, and outcomes. These components play a significant role in psychological safety by giving individuals a sense of control and agency over their work, allowing them to voice their ideas and take initiative without the fear of reprisal or judgment. Ertürk (2023) designed in the causal relational survey model to determine the relationship between teacher autonomy and dedication to the teaching profession. According to the results of the research, although it is a positive result that teachers' autonomy is at a high level in the dimensions of scale total, teaching process, and professional communication autonomy, it is a remarkable result that it is at a medium level in the dimensions of curriculum autonomy and professional development auton-

omy. Teachers' perceptions of dedication to the profession are high in all dimensions, including commitment to the profession, devotion to students, and self-sacrificing work on the total scale. In general, there is a positive, moderate, and high level significant relationship between the whole and dimensions of the teacher autonomy scale and the scale of dedication to the teaching profession. Teacher autonomy is a significant predictor of commitment to the teaching profession. Teacher autonomy scale sub-dimensions: the scale of dedication to the teaching profession significantly predicts the dimensions of commitment to the profession, dedication to students, and selfless work. Valdmann et al. (2020) seeks to put forward a justified definition for the concept of Teacher Ownership, and establishes levels of science teacher

ownership, based on a hierarchy of categories, using phenomenographic analysis. Such ownership is based on a meaningful science teacher internalisation of a motivational context-based teacher approach, established via a prior CPD programme. The main conclusions are that sustainable teacher ownership differs from terms such as a sense of ownership, towards ownership and self-efficacy and that, in this study, teacher ownership can be described as being exhibited by the science teachers in paradigmatic, experiential and emotional ownership categories. Faculty instructors of a master's-level teacher research course share findings from a study on the impact of teacher research on classroom practice and teacher autonomy. DiLucchio and Leaman (2022) describe the master of education program and research capstone course, in which graduate students (practicing teachers) complete a semester-long research project. Findings derived from surveys and interviews suggest that teachers (a) adapt their instructional practices and their thinking about learners' needs and (b) develop confidence and a greater sense of autonomy following a semester-long research experience. When individuals have autonomy and ownership, they are more likely to engage in open dialogue, share their perspectives, and contribute to problem-solving and innovation. In psychologically safe environments, these components empower individuals to take risks, make decisions, and feel a strong sense of commitment. They foster a culture where everyone's contributions are valued, ultimately enhancing overall well-being and productivity.

3.6. *Safety to Challenge the Status Quo*— "Safety to challenge the status quo" is a component of psychological safety that encourages individuals within a group or organization to question existing norms, practices, or ideas without fear of negative consequences. It embodies an

environment where individuals are not only allowed but also encouraged to voice dissenting opinions, offer alternative solutions, or challenge conventional thinking. This component is crucial in fostering innovation and growth because it creates a space where new ideas and perspectives can emerge. In psychologically safe settings that value challenging the status quo, individuals are more likely to engage in open, candid discussions, leading to improved decision-making, problem-solving, and, ultimately, positive change. Table 5 presents the extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of safety to challenge the status quo. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: a culture that supports challenging the status quo empowers individuals to explore novel strategies and embrace change when it benefits the organization or team (4.00) and in a psychologically safe environment, individuals are encouraged to challenge existing practices and propose innovative solutions, driving continuous improvement (3.45) are oftentimes manifested; while, individuals feel free to voice their concerns, question decisions, and engage in constructive discussions without the fear of negative consequences (3.10), safety to challenge the status quo recognizes the importance of critical thinking and diverse perspectives in driving creativity and problem-solving (3.10) and environments that promote this component of psychological safety are more adaptable and better equipped to navigate changing circumstances and seize new opportunities (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.33 denotes that the extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of safety to challenge the status quo is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 5. The Extent of Senior High School Teachers’ Psychological Safety in terms of Safety to Challenge the Status Quo

No	Safety to Challenge the Status Quo	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	in a psychologically safe environment, individuals are encouraged to challenge existing practices and propose innovative solutions, driving continuous improvement.	3.45	Extensive
2	individuals feel free to voice their concerns, question decisions, and engage in constructive discussions without the fear of negative consequences.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	a culture that supports challenging the status quo empowers individuals to explore novel strategies and embrace change when it benefits the organization or team.	4.00	Extensive
4	safety to challenge the status quo recognizes the importance of critical thinking and diverse perspectives in driving creativity and problem-solving.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
5	environments that promote this component of psychological safety are more adaptable and better equipped to navigate changing circumstances and seize new opportunities.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.33	Moderately Extensive

Lebrón (2018) Daring to challenge the status quo impacts innovation. Yet, successful outcomes depend on individual risk-taking and choice to influence others to support new ideas. This "Challenging the Status Quo" exercise illustrates how leaders use power and influencing tactics to challenge norms by analyzing Donald Trump’s journey as the 45th U.S. President to defy experts and successfully influence followers to support his non-traditional candidacy: businessman lacking political experience becoming leader of the free world. Through integrating videoclips and polls, instructors make power visible, relevant, and thought-provoking as students apply power theory and influencing tactics perspectives to analyze (a) how leaders impact followers’ perceptions, (b) students mutual-influencing strategies, (c) power’s rela-

tionship with social identity and privilege, and (d) social impact on innovation via activism and free speech. The status quo is no longer an option. School leaders need to model care, courage, and open communication. Superintendent Jennifer Gallagher reflects on three important components of adaptive and effective leadership communication, care, and courage that she found helpful in navigating her district through the challenges of the pandemic (Gallagher, 2023). Philosophers of education have long contemplated how the normative charge of education might include disruption of the status quo. Thinking about our work as being in battle with the status quo, though, is problematic. Partly, the author agrees with thinkers like George S. Counts that education can be a vehicle for social reconstruction. In concluding,

Smith (2019) turns to AnaLouise Keating’s pedagogies of invitation to find a place for the good of social reconstruction, its critiques, and Brighthouse’s discontinuous ethos. This is not an essay in which the author disproves Counts, then Brighthouse, to show Keating the victor. Rather, he is trying to build upon and strengthen each of these thinkers to demonstrate another way of achieving change.

Table 6 shows the summary of the extent of senior high school teachers’ psychological safety. The result is focused on the highest and

lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: autonomy and ownership (3.47), and team cohesion and trust (3.41) are oftentimes manifested; while, supportive leadership (3.39), respectful and constructive feedback (3.29) and safety to challenge the status quo (3.33) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.37 denotes the extent to which senior high school teachers’ psychological safety is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 6. Summary on the Extent of Senior High School Teachers’ Psychological Safety

No	Senior High School Teachers’ Psychological Safety	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	respectful and constructive feedback	3.29	Moderately Extensive
2	supportive leadership	3.39	Moderately Extensive
3	team cohesion and trust	3.41	Extensive
4	autonomy and ownership	3.47	Extensive
5	safety to challenge the status quo	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.37	Moderately Extensive

Psychological safety is a foundational element for creating supportive and inclusive environments that foster collaboration, creativity, and overall well-being. It plays a pivotal role in enhancing teamwork, decision-making, and overall productivity, as it encourages individuals to share their perspectives and make valuable contributions without fear or apprehension. Psychological Safety is one of the most important conditions for team learning and has also been tied to improved organizational outcomes. Shahid and Din (2021) explore the influence of school leadership’s task and relations-oriented behavior, leadership styles, and the schools’ organizational culture on teachers’ psychological safety. The findings indicated a strong effect of leadership task-oriented and relation-oriented behavior and the teachers’ psychological safety

with team effectiveness as a significant moderator as well as a predictor of psychological safety. Further analysis showed that a collaborative and cultivating school culture has higher levels of teachers’ psychological safety. Therefore, school administration may consciously develop a collaborative and innovation-oriented school culture and disseminate it through a Team Leadership style that is oriented towards the teachers and the achievement of organizational goals. The theoretical contribution of this research is examining the construct of psychological safety amongst school teachers in relation to antecedents at the organizational and team levels.

3.7. *Work Engagement*—Work engagement is a concept that encapsulates the positive and profound connection between an individual

and their work or professional role. It reflects a state of mind where employees or individuals, in general, invest themselves emotionally, cognitively, and physically in their tasks and responsibilities. Engaged individuals exhibit a high level of enthusiasm, dedication, and focus in their work, often going above and beyond the basic job requirements. They are intrinsically motivated, taking deep satisfaction from their work and finding a sense of meaning and fulfillment in what they do. Work engagement goes beyond mere job satisfaction; it represents a holistic and energizing experience that encompasses a sense of purpose, connection, and a genuine desire to excel in one's responsibilities (Hosseini, et.al., 2021). Vigor as a component of work engagement, represents the energetic and resilient aspect of an individual's relationship with their work. It embodies a sense of liveliness, enthusiasm, and high levels of physical and mental energy that individuals bring to their tasks and responsibilities. When individuals experience vigor in their work, they exhibit a zest for tackling challenges and a strong motivation to invest their efforts actively (Sanli, 2019). They are proactive, dynamic, and often go the extra mile to accomplish their goals.

Increasing the energy that employees have towards their work has become an important issue today. As in every field, it has started to feel compulsory in the education sector. The work engagement is to transfer the desire and energy of the teacher to his work. It will only be possible for the teacher to feel attracted to his job in an educational atmosphere where the person is supported. For this reason, this study was carried out in order to examine the perceptions of teachers working in primary and secondary schools about work engagement. As a result of the research are examined, a significant difference was found between the variables of gender, branch, graduated school, se-

This component is characterized by a feeling of being invigorated by one's work rather than drained by it. Table 7 presents the extent of work engagement in terms of vigor. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: those with high levels of vigor often serve as positive role models and sources of inspiration for their colleagues, fostering a motivated and engaged team (4.10) and individuals with vigor are more resilient and able to bounce back from setbacks, demonstrating a tenacious and determined attitude (3.45) are oftentimes manifested; while, engaged individuals exhibit high levels of energy and a deep passion for their tasks and responsibilities (3.15), vigorous employees are highly motivated and take initiative to accomplish their goals and meet challenges head-on (3.10) and when vigor is present, it contributes to a more positive and dynamic workplace, leading to increased job satisfaction and overall well-being among employees (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.36 denotes that the extent of work engagement in terms of vigor is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

niority and age according to the opinions of teachers about the "Vigor" sub-dimension. According to the opinions of teachers belonging to the sub-dimension of "devotion", a significant difference was found between the variables of school, seniority and age. In the "concentration" sub-dimension, a significant difference was found between the variables of branch, seniority, and age. The levels of attractiveness towards their work in the schools in which the teachers worked resulted in a positive level (Nanto et al., 2020). Vigor is a vital element of work engagement as it not only drives productivity but also contributes to an individual's overall well-being, job satisfaction, and resilience in

Table 7. The extent of Work Engagement in Terms of Vigor

No	Vigor	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	engaged individuals exhibit high levels of energy and a deep passion for their tasks and responsibilities.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
2	vigorous employees are highly motivated and take initiative to accomplish their goals and meet challenges head-on.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	individuals with vigor are more resilient and able to bounce back from setbacks, demonstrating a tenacious and determined attitude.	3.45	Extensive
4	those with high levels of vigor often serve as positive role models and sources of inspiration for their colleagues, fostering a motivated and engaged team.	4.10	Extensive
5	when vigor is present, it contributes to a more positive and dynamic workplace, leading to increased job satisfaction and overall well-being among employees.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.36	Moderately Extensive

the face of workplace demands and stressors. It represents a positive and constructive aspect of work engagement, fostering a sense of fulfillment and accomplishment in one’s professional life. Sanli (2019) determine the relationship between the elementary, middle and high school teachers’ personal empowerment perception and passion for working. The results of the analyses revealed that the average of the Personal Empowerment scale extent ranges around “frequently”. The perception level of the participants related to personal empowerment scale was in the range of “high”. All the averages related to the measurement of engagement were in the range of “frequently”. It was observed that participants evaluated their level related to the measurement of engagement in high ebb. When the values related to gender variable points to personal empowerment scale’s “choice” extent, it suggested that average values related to the perceptions of male teachers are higher than that of the female teachers. It was seen that

”effect” behaviors of teachers predicts ”vigor” meaningfully. Further, that ”content” behaviors of teachers predicts ”absorption” meaningfully.

3.8. *Absorption*—Absorption, as a component of work engagement, reflects a state where individuals become fully engrossed and deeply focused on their work or tasks. It signifies a sense of flow, where individuals lose track of time and are completely immersed in what they are doing. When people experience absorption in their work, they become captivated by the challenges and demands of their roles, finding great satisfaction in their efforts. They are able to concentrate with remarkable intensity, experiencing a sense of total engrossment that allows them to be highly productive and creative (Su Jiang, 2023). Grounded in self-determination theory, this study examines the effects of a leisure-time physical activity (LTPA) intervention with work colleagues on work-related outcomes of relatedness satisfaction, engagement factors, satisfaction, and burnout subtypes. Re-

sults highlight that two weekly sessions of LTPA with work colleagues can lead to positive work-related outcomes among teachers (Abós et al., 2021). Table 8 presents the extent of work engagement in terms of absorption. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: absorbed individuals are more likely to generate new ideas and insights, as they are fully engaged in their work and capable of thinking creatively (4.10), and this component of work engagement is associated with increased productivity and the ability to complete tasks with greater efficiency and quality (4.00) are oftentimes manifested; while, absorption enhances the sense of intrinsic sat-

isfaction and personal fulfillment derived from one’s work, making it highly rewarding (3.10), engaged individuals experience a state of flow, where they become completely absorbed in their tasks, often losing track of time (3.00) and the experience of absorption is central to work engagement, as it represents the deep investment and emotional connection individuals have with their work, ultimately leading to higher levels of well-being and job satisfaction (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.44 denotes that the extent of work engagement in absorption is often manifested and, thus, extensive.

Table 8. The Extent of Work Engagement in Terms of Absorption

No	Absorption	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	engaged individuals experience a state of flow, where they become completely absorbed in their tasks, often losing track of time.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	absorption enhances the sense of intrinsic satisfaction and personal fulfillment derived from one’s work, making it highly rewarding.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	this component of work engagement is associated with increased productivity and the ability to complete tasks with greater efficiency and quality.	4.00	Extensive
4	absorbed individuals are more likely to generate new ideas and insights, as they are fully engaged in their work and capable of thinking creatively.	4.10	Extensive
5	the experience of absorption is central to work engagement, as it represents the deep investment and emotional connection individuals have with their work, ultimately leading to higher levels of well-being and job satisfaction.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.44	Extensive

Lin, Cai and Yin (2021) examined the relationship between career mentoring and work engagement from the mentor perspective, by estimating work meaningfulness as a mediator. The results demonstrated that career mentoring had an indirect effect on the work engagement of mentors by enhancing the psychological meaningfulness of their work. In addition, learning goal orientation positively influenced career mentoring; this may subsequently facilitate the work engagement by increasing the perception of the meaning of work. Learning-oriented individuals who act as mentors find psychological meaningfulness in their work, which in turn enhances their work engagement. By setting acceptable meaningful goals for mentoring programmes, practitioners can minimize the negative outcomes of mentoring. The results contribute to the existing literature by examining how mentoring experiences affect the behaviour of mentors. Su and Jiang (2023) takes work-family conflict as the independent variable, work engagement as the dependent variable, and perceived organizational support and emotional exhaustion as the mediating variables, and studies the influence of work-family conflict on work engagement and the mechanism of perceived organizational support and emotional exhaustion of female university teachers in China, based on the job demand-resource model (JD-R). The results of the questionnaire survey of 518 female university teachers revealed a significant negative relationship between work-family conflict and work engagement, with a direct effect accounting for 31.88%. The two studies presented here examine the effects of teachers' enhanced sense of meaning at work (SOM) on their burnout and engagement. Hierarchical

linear modeling analyses showed that teachers' daily SOM was associated with increased engagement on the following day and somewhat increased stress. Thus, the studies highlight teachers' SOM as a resource that contributes to engagement and can be enhanced intentionally (Lavy, 2022). Table 9 presents the extent of work engagement in terms of sense of meaning. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: engaged individuals experience positive emotions associated with their tasks, such as fulfillment, pride, and a deep sense of accomplishment (4.10) and engaged individuals have a profound understanding of the significance of their work and how it contributes to their organization or society (3.40) are often-times manifested; while, a sense of meaning and purpose aligns one's personal values with their work, creating a powerful connection that drives motivation and commitment (3.10), a sense of meaning and purpose often results in individuals taking proactive steps to make a meaningful contribution and create a positive impact through their work (3.10) and individuals with a strong sense of purpose are more likely to commit to their work, leading to increased loyalty and dedication (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.34 denotes that the extent of work engagement in terms of sense of meaning is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Chandra Handa (2023) argued that wisdom development should be the ultimate goal of educating gifted learners. It is not merely what talents gifted learners develop, but how they use these talents, which will determine how meaningfully they lead their lives, and contribute to the lives of others in society.

A theoretically grounded Leading Wisdom Development Framework (LWDF) is presented which articulates developmental levels of wisdom: emerging wisdom, developing wis-

dom, enhancing wisdom, and advancing wisdom. The framework outlines leadership actions which include deepening teaching quality and collective teacher capacity, strengthening

Table 9. The Extent of Work Engagement in Terms of Sense of Meaning

No	Sense of Meaning	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	engaged individuals have a profound understanding of the significance of their work and how it contributes to their organization or society.	3.40	Extensive
2	a sense of meaning and purpose aligns one’s personal values with their work, creating a powerful connection that drives motivation and commitment.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	individuals with a strong sense of purpose are more likely to commit to their work, leading to increased loyalty and dedication.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
4	engaged individuals experience positive emotions associated with their tasks, such as fulfillment, pride, and a deep sense of accomplishment.	4.10	Extensive
5	a sense of meaning and purpose often results in individuals taking proactive steps to make a meaningful contribution and create a positive impact through their work.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.34	Moderately Extensive

programming, enabling student agency, collaborating with the wider community, and anchoring changes into the school culture. Effective leaders create conditions for integrated wisdom and talent development of gifted learners so that they can use their talents for the greater good of others. On the other hand, Yanci and Dal (2020) aimed to investigate the effects of leisure meanings on work engagement of teachers from different branches. The study results suggested a significant and positive correlation between the meaning of leisure and work engagement. Teaching is life-giving work, essential for the development of thriving humans. It is devastating to hear teachers refer to themselves as “just teachers” as if they are powerless and without status. Teachers who are just, cultivate freedom, justice, and flourishing (Eckert, 2023). Lastly, ensuring teachers’ job engagement is critical in achieving educational

goals. Karatas and Özdemir (2022) examined the relationship between meaningful work and job engagement using the data collected from 452 teachers in Turkey. They found a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between meaningful work and job engagement. They tested the predictive effects of meaningful work and demographic variables (gender, seniority, and educational status). Meaningful work explained 47 percent of the variance in teachers’ job engagement in the first model.

3.9. *Healthy in Work-Life Balance*—A healthy work-life balance, as a component of work engagement, signifies the equilibrium individuals strike between their professional responsibilities and their personal lives, including family, leisure, and well-being. It emphasizes the importance of not allowing work to dominate one’s life to the detriment of personal and family time, relaxation, and self-care. When

individuals maintain a healthy work-life balance, they are more likely to feel refreshed, less stressed, and more engaged in both their work and personal life. They can manage their job demands effectively, yet also carve out time for themselves, their loved ones, and their interests outside of work. Table 10 presents the extent of work engagement in terms of healthy work-life balance. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: maintaining a balanced approach to work and life helps individuals avoid burnout, resulting in increased job satisfaction and a reduced likelihood of experiencing excessive stress (4.10), engaged employees are better equipped to meet their personal, family, and social commitments, leading to a greater sense of accomplishment and well-being (3.50) and

Kandemir et al. (2022) aims to determine the role of distance education in teachers' work-life balance. Based on the findings, suggestions were made such as conducting in-service training seminars for teachers to ensure effective work-life balance and reducing teachers' responsibilities, especially in the area of stationery. The balance between personal life and work life is essential to achieve desired outcomes. However, the COVID-19 global pandemic changed the way people live and work and affected schools like other organizations. Teachers were expected to work from home and adapt to the tools and technologies used in distance education. Working from home has blurred the borders between work and personal life and might affect the work-life balance adversely. Although there are studies based on the work-life balance of academicians, there is a gap lack of in the experiences of teachers on work-life balance during emergency remote teaching, especially those who worked at private schools. Ünal and Dulay (2022) identify teachers' experiences on work-life balance in

a balanced approach to work and personal life allows individuals to recharge and rejuvenate, ultimately enhancing their productivity and engagement in the workplace (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, organizations that support a balanced lifestyle for their employees often create a more positive and supportive work environment, promoting higher levels of engagement and well-being among their staff (3.10) and engaged individuals strike a balance between their work-related commitments and personal life, preventing excessive work demands from encroaching on personal time (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.42 denotes that the extent of work engagement in terms of healthy work-life balance is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

emergency remote teaching. The findings of the study revealed that there were two themes as (i) challenges for work-life balance and (ii) ways of maintaining a work-life balance. It was found that the teachers, who had to work from home, did not maintain a balance between personal life and work because of such challenges as inadequacy of workspace, irregularity of working hours, lack of support and role conflicts. Consequently, they failed to achieve the desired outcomes of work and individual lives which adversely affected their well-being. Besides, working from home and distance education seem likely to continue even after the pandemic has ended. Teachers face a multitude of challenges during this unprecedented time with a rapid shift from traditional face-to-face class to online learning resulting in a cyclical phenomenon for many teachers as schools have shifted back and forth between virtual and in-person settings in response to constantly changing coronavirus messaging. The findings identified three overarching themes related to teachers' needs including "Boundaries with Time and Commit-

Table 10. Extent of Work Engagement in Terms of Healthy Work-life Balance

No	Healthy Work-life Balance	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	engaged individuals strike a balance between their work-related commitments and personal life, preventing excessive work demands from encroaching on personal time.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	a balanced approach to work and personal life allows individuals to recharge and rejuvenate, ultimately enhancing their productivity and engagement in the workplace.	3.40	Extensive
3	engaged employees are better equipped to meet their personal, family, and social commitments, leading to a greater sense of accomplishment and well-being.	3.50	Extensive
4	maintaining a balanced approach to work and life helps individuals avoid burnout, resulting in increased job satisfaction and a reduced likelihood of experiencing excessive stress.	4.10	Extensive
5	organizations that support a balanced lifestyle for their employees often create a more positive and supportive work environment, promoting higher levels of engagement and well-being among their staff.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.42	Extensive

ments,” ”Mentally Processing Daily Stressors,” and ”Healthy Lifestyle.” Implications for practice denote that school leaders need to evaluate the current level of support provided to teachers and assess areas of need to provide professional learning that is purposeful, collaborative, and sustainable (McBrayer et al., 2022). This balance is crucial for preventing burnout and maintaining overall well-being, as it enables individuals to recharge, enjoy personal time, and return to work with renewed energy and enthusiasm. Healthy work-life balance is a vital aspect of work engagement as it promotes not only job satisfaction but also personal fulfillment and a holistic sense of well-being, contributing to a productive and fulfilling professional and personal life.

3.10. Summary of the Extent of Work Engagement—Table 11 shows a summary of the extent of work engagement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: absorption (3.44) and healthy work-life balance (3.42) are often manifested, while vigor (3.36) and sense of meaning (3.34) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.39 denotes that the extent of work engagement is sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. Teachers’ perceived levels of emotional exhaustion and cognitive work engagement were assessed in relation to several professional competencies (self-efficacy with using inclusive instruction, collaborating with parents and paraprofessionals, and managing disruptive behaviors), as well

as the organizational variable of role understanding. Regression analysis showed that teachers' self-efficacy with using inclusive instruction was found to be the most powerful negative predictor of emotional exhaustion, while self-efficacy for managing disruptive behaviors was a positive predictor of teachers' cognitive work engagement.

Table 11. Summary of the Extent of Work Engagement

No	Work Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	vigor	3.36	Moderately Extensive
2	absorption	3.44	Extensive
3	sense of meaning	3.34	Moderately Extensive
4	healthy work-life balance	3.42	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.39	Moderately Extensive

Teachers' level of understanding of their role and that of their schools was a negative predictor of emotional exhaustion and a positive predictor of cognitive work engagement. Moreover, it further confirmed that the concept of co-existence between work engagement and burnout can be applied to inclusive teachers. Results were interpreted in relation to management in inclusive schools in Macao and were followed by a discussion on the implications of enhancing inclusive education. Basaran and Kiral (2020) examine the relationship between the authentic leadership behaviors of the school administrator and the work engagement of the teachers, according to the perceptions of the teachers of secondary school. The research was designed in the relational survey model and carried out with 300 teachers. As a result of the research, it was found that teachers' general perceptions of authentic leadership of school administrators was relatively high and the highest level on balanced processing. Teachers' general perceptions work engagement was relatively high and the highest level on dedication. Positive, medium and low-level relationships were found between authentic leadership and work engagement. According to teachers, the authentic leadership of school administrators significantly predicted teachers' perceptions of work

engagement. Based on these findings it has been proposed to various suggestions have been put forward such as protect and increase the authentic leadership behaviors of school administrators and teachers' work engagement levels. Sittar (2020) find out the relationship of work engagement and job performance of university teachers. Quantitative approach was selected and correlation research design was used. The findings of the study indicated that there was a weak positive correlation between work engagements with job performance of university teachers. Uanci and Dal (2020) aimed to investigate the effects of leisure meanings on work engagement of teachers from different branches. The study results suggested a significant and positive correlation between the meaning of leisure and work engagement. Engaged individuals are more likely to be productive, innovative, and resilient, contributing to their personal well-being as well as the overall success of the organizations they work for. Work engagement is a critical aspect of a healthy and thriving work environment, and it is associated with improved job performance and job satisfaction.

3.11. Significant Relationship between Teachers' Psychological Safety and Work Engagement—It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correla-

tion between teachers’ psychological safety (r=0.858; p<.000) and work engagement. Table 12 revealed the significant relationship between teachers’ psychological safety and work engagement. It provides information that the

posed null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between teachers’ psychological safety and work engagement, must be rejected, for it provided empirical evidence to show its correlation.

Table 12. Significant Relationship between Teachers’ Psychological Safety and Work Engagement

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Work Engagement	0.868	<0.000	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant at $p < 0.05$.

Hosseini et al. (2021) stated that the significant relationship between teachers’ psychological safety and work engagement plays a crucial role in fostering a positive and productive educational environment. Psychological safety, defined as the perception that one can express oneself without fear of negative consequences, creates a foundation for open communication and collaboration among educators. When teachers feel psychologically safe, they are more likely to share innovative ideas, seek support, and engage in constructive dialogue (Marsick Watkins, 2003). Gaynor et al. (2022) use this sense of safety to contribute to a positive work culture, enhancing overall well-being. Work engagement, characterized by a deep connection and enthusiasm for one’s job, is bolstered by the supportive atmosphere created through psychological safety. Teachers who feel secure in expressing their thoughts and concerns are more likely to invest emotionally in their work, leading to increased job satisfaction, motivation, and improved educational outcomes (Chung, 2023). Recognizing and nurturing the reciprocal relationship between psychological safety and work

engagement is essential for creating a resilient and thriving teaching community.

3.12. *Domains of Teachers’ Psychological Safety Significantly Influence Work Engagement*—Table 13 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on domains of teachers’ psychological safety significantly influencing work engagement. Domains of teachers’ psychological safety in terms of respectful and constructive feedback (0.000), supportive leadership (0.000), team cohesion and trust (0.002), autonomy and ownership (0.000), and safety to challenge the status quo (0.000) significantly influenced work engagement. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.867 suggests that 86.7 percent of teachers’ psychological safety can explain work engagement. This provides empirical evidence that teachers’ psychological safety can account for and explain variability in work engagement. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (254.676) and F-statistic are significant $p < .000$, which indicates that the model better predicts work engagement.

Teachers’ psychological safety significantly influences work engagement in the educational setting. Psychological safety refers to the per-

ception that individuals can voice their thoughts, opinions, and concerns without fear of reprisal. When teachers experience a psychologically

Table 13. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Teachers' Psychological Safety Significantly Influence Work Engagement

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	Decisions
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	4.143
H	(Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.201
1*Respectful and Constructive Feedback	0.817	0.117	1.010	0.315	0.000	*Reject H
1*Supportive Leadership	0.431	0.118	1.275	0.196	0.000	*Reject H
1*Team Cohesion and Trust	0.212	0.097	2.086	0.038	0.002	*Reject H
1*Autonomy and Ownership	0.921	0.508	1.259	0.296	0.000	*Reject H
1*Challenge the Status Quo	0.502	0.057	3.068	0.038	0.000	*Reject H
R² = 0.867		F-value = 254.676		p-value = <0.000		

*Significant at $p < 0.05$.

safe environment, they are more likely to engage in open communication, collaboration, and risk-taking behaviors. This, in turn, fosters a positive work culture where teachers feel valued and supported. Psychologically safe allows educators to share innovative ideas, seek help, and collaborate effectively with colleagues. As teachers experience a sense of security in expressing themselves, it positively impacts their work engagement. Work engagement, characterized by

vigor, dedication, and absorption in one's job, becomes more prevalent when teachers feel a strong connection to their work and a sense of purpose. In essence, the psychological safety of teachers creates a conducive environment for heightened work engagement, contributing to a more vibrant and compelling educational community. Therefore, recognizing and prioritizing psychological safety is integral to cultivating a positive and engaged teaching workforce.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analysis, discussion, and drawing of implications. Findings were based on the problem's posed statement; conclusions were based on the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of senior high school teachers' psycho-

logical safety in terms of autonomy and ownership (3.47), and team cohesion and trust (3.41) are oftentimes manifested; while, supportive leadership (3.39), respectful and constructive

feedback (3.29), and safety to challenge the status quo (3.33) were sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.37 denotes the extent to which senior high school teachers' psychological safety was sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of work engagement in terms of absorption (3.44) and healthy work-life balance (3.42) are oftentimes manifested, while vigor (3.36) and sense of meaning (3.34) were sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.39 denotes the extent of work engagement, which was sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' psychological safety ($r=0.858$; $p<.000$) and work engagement. Domains of teachers' psychological safety in terms of respectful and constructive feedback (0.000), supportive leadership (0.000), team cohesion and trust (0.002), autonomy and ownership (0.000), and safety to challenge the status quo (0.000) significantly influenced work engagement.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions to wit; The extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety in terms of autonomy and ownership, and team cohesion and trust are oftentimes manifested, while supportive leadership, respectful and constructive feedback, and safety to challenge the status quo were sometimes manifested. The extent of senior high school teachers' psychological safety was sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of work engagement in terms of absorption and healthy work-life balance was often manifested, while vigor and a sense of meaning were sometimes manifested. Thus, the extent of work engagement was sometimes moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' psychological safety and work engagement. Domains of teachers' psychological safety, such as respectful and constructive feedback, supportive

leadership, team cohesion and trust, autonomy and ownership, and safety to challenge the status quo, significantly influenced work engagement.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May advocate for professional development programs that promote psychological safety within the teaching staff. Encourage a leadership style emphasizing open communication, support, and acknowledgment of teachers' contributions. Implement policies and practices that foster a positive and inclusive work environment, addressing any potential sources of stress or conflict. School Principal. May prioritize creating a school culture that values psychological safety by organizing workshops and training sessions. Foster an atmosphere of trust and collaboration among teachers, recognizing and appreciating their efforts. Establish support systems for teachers, such as mentorship programs and regular check-ins, to address individual needs and concerns. Teacher. May actively participate in professional development opportunities that enhance emotional intelligence, communication skills, and conflict resolution. Foster a sense of community and collaboration within the school, encouraging peer support and teamwork. Advocate for open communication with school leadership, expressing needs and concerns to contribute to a positive and supportive work environment. Future Researcher. May investigate the long-term effects of interventions to improve teachers' psychological safety on overall school performance. Explore additional factors that may influence or moderate the relationship between psychological safety and work engagement. Conduct comparative studies across different school settings and demographics to understand the generalizability of findings and identify potential variations.

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